

ISic3127

I.Sicily inscription 3127

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333766

1. . . . μ[η]-

2. νὶ τῆς τρισ [ί] ²sc. ἡμέραις².

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645468

PHI 333766

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 31.0843

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 765 no.29

Feissel, D. 1981. Trois aspects de l'influence du latin sur le grec tardif. *Travaux et mémoires du Centre de recherches d'histoire et civilisation byzantines*. 8: 135-150.
At 147 n.129

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